

Exam Protocol

Patient Info:

Name: [REDACTED]

Sex: M ID: P47751

Patient Position: HFS

05-Dec-19 13:40:18

2	3D	FIXED	6sDCT Body	6s	60F/s	05-Dec-19 14:02:32
A	92kV 304mA	3.7ms	0.1CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	2961.4µGym ²	96.0mGy	169LAO 0CRA 397F
3	3D	FIXED	6sDCT Body	6s	60F/s	05-Dec-19 14:15:13
A	92kV 352mA	3.7ms	0.1CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	3165.7µGym ²	103mGy	169LAO 0CRA 397F
4	3D	FIXED	6sDCT Body	6s	60F/s	05-Dec-19 14:21:24
A	93kV 343mA	3.7ms	0.2CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	3136.6µGym ²	102mGy	169LAO 0CRA 397F
5	3D	FIXED	6sDCT Body	6s	60F/s	05-Dec-19 14:29:22
A	93kV 342mA	3.7ms	0.2CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	3140.1µGym ²	102mGy	169LAO 0CRA 397F
6	3D	FIXED	5sDCT Body Care	4s	60F/s	05-Dec-19 14:43:07
A	90kV 338mA	3.7ms	0.2CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	1899.8µGym ²	61.6mGy	169LAO 0CRA 248F

Accumulated exposure data

05-Dec-19 14:44:29

Performing Physician: D'Angelo

Exposures: 5

Total Fluoro: 00:00:22

Total: 14474µGym² 469.2mGy

A Fluoro: 00:00:22 170.07µGym²

5.5mGy

Total: 14474µGym² 469.2mGy